

AUSTRALIAN BIBLICAL REVIEW

Vol. 51, 2003

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Published annually in November

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The *Australian Biblical Review* (ABR) is a refereed journal.
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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The Fellowship gratefully acknowledges support for this issue of the *ABR* from:

Jesuit Theological College
Uniting Church Theological Hall

ISSN 0045-0308

A SAMARITAN BROADSIDE FROM THE MID SECOND CENTURY A.D.

Ruairidh Bóid

I. THE PROBLEM

The long treatise *Against Kelsos*,¹ or in its full title *Against the Text by Kelsos Known as the True Utterance (Pros ton Epigegrammenon Kelsou Alêthê Logon)*, was probably written by Origen some time between AD 244 and 248. This treatise preserves the full text, aside from a few sentences that are condensed, of a shorter treatise written by a philosopher called Kelsos, at the latest between AD 176 and 180.²

The purpose of Kelsos's composition was to show the incompatibility of Christianity with reason, accepted standards of piety, and universally accepted philosophical principles. Near the start of this composition, however, Kelsos raises the question of the historical sources of Christianity. Two inter-related questions regarding the reliability of the New Testament, especially the Gospels, and the acceptability of Christianity's right to claim to be the true working-out of the history of Israel and, therefore, the true manifestation of the intent of the scriptures of that tradition, from Moses onwards, are posed. To sort these questions out, Kelsos re-produces a brief composition, short enough to be read aloud comfortably, with expansions and pauses, in three-quarters of an hour, or to be printed on six pages of A4 paper. He claims that it is Jewish in origin and sets out, from the Jewish point of view, the arguments against the reasonableness and historicity of the christological predicates. Origen declares this composition to be a fiction, composed by Kelsos himself and set in the form of a diatribe by an anonymous Jewish orator for rhetorical effect. All later authors have agreed with Origen. However, Origen was misled by

¹The edition used is Origène, *Contre Celse, introduction, texte critique, traduction et notes* par Marcel Borret, s.j., Editions du Cerf, Paris, (5 vols.) 1967-1976. (Sources Chrétiennes, nos. 132, 136, 147, 150, 227). The dating of Kelsos by Borret between AD 176 and 180 is not supported by direct evidence or compelling argument. There is evidence for a date in the reign of Antoninus Pius (AD 138-161). Note that the anonymous Samaritan treatise is cited according to the divisions of Origen's book. All translations are mine, throughout this article, though I have consulted both the translation by Borret and the one in *The Antenicene Fathers*.

²The title *Alêthês Logos (True Utterance)* may well be an abbreviation of the full title.

his limited knowledge of the theological variety within Judaism before the Rabbinic version in its consolidated form.³ As a result, statements that seemed a bit odd to him deserve to be re-examined in the light of current knowledge, rather than dismissed as mistakes. Nevertheless, there is one sentence that is obviously nonsense, and yet is positioned so prominently right at the start that the reader is immediately inclined to dismiss, along with Origen, the whole composition as not only fictional, but incompetent. This is the sentence “On the contrary, my Prophet once said in Jerusalem that the Son of God would come as judge of the saints and punisher of the unrighteous” at 1:49 (*All’ eipen emos Prophêtês en Hierosolymois pote hoti hêxei Theou Hyios tôn hosiôn kritês kai tôn adikôn kolastês*).

The difficulty for us, however, is not, as it was for Origen, to account for the alleged carelessness. We can see that he was not careless elsewhere, and is therefore probably not careless here. Instead, the difficulty is to account for the corruption of the author’s meaning into the manifest nonsense as it appears in the extant text. If this sentence can be sorted out, then the whole question of the genuineness of the composition will have to be looked at again.

II. THE SOLUTION

Most authors don’t write nonsense, and definitely not authors whose writings have been judged worth keeping. Sometimes what seems to be nonsense can become clear when technical references and technical terms are recognized. Sometimes faulty translation of the text in an early stage of transmission is the explanation. Faulty translation is usually due to inadequate knowledge of technical terms or inadequate knowledge of the subject under discussion, or inadequate command of the source language. This last explanation is regrettably applicable to many modern translations but not often applicable to ancient ones.⁴ Let us try the hypothesis of translation from Aramaic to Greek, with inadequate recognition of technical terms.

Translating the first part of the sentence into Aramaic, we get (‘L’) (‘RWM) NBY’Y ’MR (BYWM) (LYWM) BYRWSHLM: this was what the translator thought he saw. For what was meant, consider this sentence: “If someone has predicted to you that the Son of God would come to mankind, it was our Prophet, the Prophet of our God” (2:4). Plausibly, then, in 1:49 what was intended was NBY’ Y “the Prophet of the Lord”.

³Actually, even in regard to the later Rabbinic standard form, Origen’s knowledge is superficial, and he is in general unaware of the variety of theological views that it accommodates.

⁴One thinks specifically of some modern published translations of Samaritan texts from Arabic, Hebrew, and Aramaic, including some that are generally quoted as sources in secondary literature, to the detriment of scholarship.

Such usage is foreign to Rabbinic Judaism but normal in Samaritan texts.⁵ Perhaps what was written was actually **NBY' YHWH 'MR** (which would be quite normal in Samaritan usage in a serious composition), read by the translator as **NBY'Y HWH 'MR**, putting the verb in the continuous past tense.

Let us continue along the lines of the work of a Jewish translator, or even a translator familiar with Judaism, but unfamiliar with even very basic Samaritan technical terminology. It seems likely that they missed a reference to the extremely important concept of the Day of Vengeance and Recompense (**YWM NQM WShLM**) in the words "as judge of the saints and punisher of the unrighteous". This is a specifically Samaritan term, and is taken from a verse of the Torah, Deuteronomy 32:35, which has a different form in the Jewish text. Instead of **LYWM NQM WShLM** "to the Day of Vengeance and Recompense", the Jewish text has **LY NQM WShLM** "Mine is Vengeance and Recompense". Once again, a Jewish translator would not recognize an allusion to this verse.⁶ Translating the three words into Aramaic, following the example of the Samaritan Targum in this verse and neighbouring verses, we get **LYWM GBY WShLM**, which when squashed up becomes **LYWM GBYWShLM**. If we take the intention to be to refer to the pericope by a conventional fixed designation, we get **BYWM ShLM**. Either way, a translator seeing these words, and not recognising the reference intended, will come up with the meaning "once in Jerusalem".

The second of these explanations is much neater, and when examined presents no difficulty at all. It relies on taking **ShLM** "recompensing" in v.35 in a double meaning, favourable and unfavourable, while **NQM** "vengeance" in v.35 is ambiguous (compare the ways the Peshitta trans-

⁵Both Jews and Samaritans agree that there were prophets before Moses. Although all forms of Judaism agree on the uniqueness of Moses and the supreme status of the Pentateuch, Judaism accepts a series of lesser prophets, of a lower grade of inspiration, ending with Haggai, Zechariah, and Malachi. It would therefore be confusing to refer to Moses as "the Prophet" or "our Prophet", and he is usually called "our Master" (Rabbenu). The Samaritans don't recognize any of these lesser prophets, and so can refer to Moses simply as "the Prophet", without any confusion. The Samaritans write the Tetragrammaton in full quite normally in serious contexts. In Rabbinic Judaism it is not written (except in editions of scriptural quotations anywhere else it is always abbreviated or changed). A Jew in the second century would not expect to see the Tetragrammaton even in abbreviated form in the present context, and certainly would never imagine that it could have been written in full. Even if he had seen **NBY' YHWH 'MR**, he would have corrected it, assuming scribal error to be responsible.

⁶A Christian translator would have picked up the allusion, since the **LXX** agrees with the Samaritan in regard to the reading **LYWM**, but a Christian would not have translated this treatise anyway. The Christian readers for whom the treatise was intended could not have missed the meaning.

lates this root throughout the O.T.), and the “judging” of v.36 is probably favourable. I am not aware of such a double meaning of **ShLM** in this verse being attested in Samaritan or Rabbinic sources (obviously this is not to say it is not written somewhere). However, this double meaning is unequivocally attested in 2 Thessalonians 1:5-10, which refers back to the LXX (and perhaps the Hebrew as well) of Deuteronomy 32:35-36 (with the reading **LYWM** being assumed in v.35). The ellipsis of the verb at the start of v.7 makes this certain. Even if there is some influence from Isaiah 61:1-2 (LXX) the combination of terms is from Deuteronomy. Furthermore, the LXX of Isaiah at 61:2 translates **YWM NQM L'LHYNW**, “the Day of Vengeance of our God”, an allusion to Deuteronomy 32:35, as “the Day of Recompense”, the word **'LHYNW** being understood, and not translated. In the context, the word “recompense” must have a favourable meaning. It is not a direct translation of **NQM** “vengeance” as often assumed: the translator has realized that **YWM NQM** is an allusion to the whole of v. 35 and its context. It follows, therefore, that the translator could assume that his readers would recognize an allusion to Deuteronomy 32:35-36 in the term “the Day of Recompense”. In the same way, the readers could be expected to pick up the reference to the Jubilee Year (Leviticus 25:10 and the following section) in his translation of the previous verse. In Isaiah 63:4, **YWM NQM BLBY** is translated as “the Day of Recompense has come to them”. In this case, although the recompense is to be welcomed by those for whom it comes, it is definitely unfavourable for those upon whom it comes. In Isaiah 35:4, (**IINH 'LHYKM**) **NQM YBW'** is translated as “(...) *krfsin antapodidōsi*” i.e. “(...) recompenses judgement”. This is not natural usage in Greek any more than it is in English. Given the overall naturalness of the LXX of Isaiah, the only explanation is that it is a deliberate evocation of Deuteronomy 32:35. To make it work **NQM** is rendered fairly literally as “judgement”, but with a translation of **ShLM**, a word not present in the Hebrew of this verse of Isaiah, also dragged in to make the allusion clear. It is true that the verb is not as prominent as it might seem from this quotation, because the word **GMWL** occurs in the same verse and is translated fairly literally, but the allusion to Deuteronomy is still artificial and still therefore deliberate. The measure of the unnaturalness of the sentence can be seen in the way the Syropalestinian Version modifies it. In this case **ShLM** must be taken in an unfavourable meaning. It is evident, therefore, that there was a term **YWM ShLM** “the Day of Recompense” that was used to refer to Deuteronomy 32:35-36 and the context. A careful reading of the translation of the Peshitta of Deuteronomy 32:35-36 shows the same usage as highly likely. The LXX and all four Targums give the same impression, though not so strongly.

We now have "On the contrary, the Prophet of the Lord said, in [the section about] the Day of (Vengeance and) Recompense, that the Son of God would come as judge of the saints and punisher of the unrighteous". The form and style of the reference have a close parallel in Luke 20:37, "That the dead are resurrected Moses himself declared in [the section about] the bush where he [i.e. Moses!] says "the Lord the God of Abraham and the God of Isaac and the God of Jacob".⁷

There remains the apparent difficulty of the term "the Son of God". This term, when looked at without preconceptions, is not impossible. Hence, "Israel is my first-born" (Exodus 4:22); "You are children of the Lord your God" (Deuteronomy 14:1); "Is he [God] not thy father?" (Deuteronomy 32:6); and "Thou art my son; this day have I begotten thee" (Psalm 2:7). As for the reason for using the term, the answer is very simple and obvious. The author is contesting the historicity of the announcement by God immediately after Jesus' immersion, by contrasting the unequivocal manifestation of status implied by the Torah with the limited and uncertain testimony in the first case. The previous sentences are: "You maintain that when you were immersed by John an apparition of a bird out of the sky flew onto you. What believable witness ever saw this apparition? Who heard a voice from the sky adopting you as Son of God? Whom, except for you and someone else out of those punished (or executed) like yourself, can you produce?" (1.41). The term is not forced, however, since it is implied in verse 6 of this same section of Deuteronomy, as quoted above. If the people collectively are the son (singular) of God, then so is the divinely appointed representative of the people. Some exceptional person is alluded to in verse 34, that is, just before the mentioning of the Day of Vengeance and Recompense. This can be read as referring not to the storing away of a quality, or of consequences of action, but of the storing away in the divine storehouse of an individual, waiting for the era of manifestation. The reference would naturally be to the appearance of the hidden Moses, or to the appearance of the one like Moses. These two conceptions are widely attested in Samaritan and Jewish texts.⁸

⁷The reader might like to look at the same verse in the Peshitta to see just how close the form of citation is. Note that the Greek "says" naturally becomes a participle (whether or not it is pointed, the participle is the natural reading), confirming the restoration of NBY' YIWH 'MR, misread as NBY'Y HWH 'MR by a translator with some feeling for what was possible in Aramaic but without knowledge of Samaritan terminology.

⁸See the section, "A Pair of Ancient Samaritan Eschatologies," in my monograph (forthcoming with Brill; tentatively entitled *Samaritan Orthodoxy and Heresy*). One might speculate that such usage of the term "Son of God" was the product of the concept of the future revival of Moses. In turn, it would resemble the animation of Adam (Genesis 2:7, and see the Palestinian Targum) who was also

III. OTHER SAMARITAN TRAITS

Having seen that the problematical sentence is Samaritan (as Origen himself saw, but without following the lead), it is time to list other Samaritan traits and determine whether the whole composition is Samaritan.

The Jews are referred to in the third person in 2:5,6,8, and 32. In most or all of these cases Origen quotes directly, and the original must have had the third person. In 2:39, the author refers to Satan in a way that indicates that the term and concept are not his. In 2:4, the wording would be decidedly odd if meant to refer to the execution of Jesus, and the reference must be to a figure outside Jewish history. "It was only fairly recently, when we punished the one leading you round like cattle, that you deserted the ancestral law". Jewish polemic usually tends not to dwell on the active role of the Jewish religious leaders in forcing the conviction of Jesus and definitely does not claim sole responsibility. The implication is that the one killed had a lot of followers even before then (see the context as well). It is odd to connect the execution of this person with the abandonment of the supreme authority of the Torah, if the figure is Jesus, since the two are not connected very closely. The implication of the immediately preceding words (at the end of 2:1) is that the people addressed accepted Jesus as the inaugurator of the new era after the execution of the person mentioned in 2:4, as a result of the execution of this person, who was apparently not Jesus and who seems to be later than Jesus. There were two events: (a) someone was executed or assassinated, and then (b) the followers of this person became Christian. A plausible reference would be to the murder of the deputy High Priest Lîbi (LWY), the great Dosithean martyr, by a faction, perhaps the majority faction, who considered him a heretic. From the little that is known of the followers of Lîbi, it would not have been a big step at all for them to become Christians.⁹ In 2:6, the anonymous composition says that as "Jesus observed all Jewish usages (ethê), including even their sacrificial services, he could not have been the Son of God". Origen is stunned by this argument, but it makes perfect sense. If Jesus accepted the validity of the Jerusalem temple, which he certainly did, even if only for the present and near future, then he shared in the supreme Jewish heresy, the rejection of the place consecrated by Abraham, Isaac, and Jacob.

the child of God (Genesis 2:7 as interpreted in Luke 3:38 but presumably from older sources). One might speculate that the same meaning was found in the term "the man of God" in Deuteronomy 33:1 and that the translation "the Prophet of God" in all the Jewish Targums is a tendentious over-translation. One might also speculate that one of the linkages between being re-formed and being a child of God was Deuteronomy 32:6, in its context.

⁹See the section, "Ancient Samaritan Eschatologies" (above), tentative pagination pp. 90-93.

IV. POSSIBLE OBJECTIONS

There are two places where Origen and those following him detected a Jewish author. One is 2:8 and needs to be quoted in full.

Many others could have seemed the same as Jesus to those that wanted to be deceived. Those that believe in the Christ blame the Jews for not having believed in Jesus as [they believe] God. But how could we, who teach everyone of someone coming from God to punish the unrighteous, ever have treated him ignobly once he arrived?

In the words immediately following (2:9) it is explained that there was no inconsistency, because Jesus did not demonstrate his status. At first sight, the use of "we" and "us" seems to indicate a Jewish source. On the other hand, the Jews are mentioned in the third person just before, when it is quite clear that Origen has not re-cast the sentence. What we have here is the rhetorical device of quoting what the person or people mentioned might say if they were to hear of the charge. This analysis is confirmed by the first sentence, which indicates that there were others that made similar claims. No messianic historical figures in Judaism claimed to be the Son of God. However, from the wording immediately preceding (2:8) and immediately following, it is clear that the anonymous composition refers to various figures claiming a status that is more than human, or at least greater than that of a military leader. Compare 1:50 (following on directly from 1:41 and 1:49):

Why should it be to you rather than to any number of others born since the prophecy that what is prophesied should apply? Some, religious loonies (*enthousiôntes*), others, out for grabs (*ageirontes*), say they have come from above as Son of God.

There were, however, such figures among the Samaritans: Simon, Dositheos, Sakta, Menander, Saturninus are known, and there could have been others. See also John 8:48 in its context. From all this, it seems that 2:8 and 1:50 can be claimed as evidence of a Samaritan source. Another possible objection is in 2:28-29.

The Christians quote the prophets as announcing beforehand the traits (or history) of Jesus (*ta peri Iêsou*). There are lots of others to whom the prophecies could be applied much more plausibly than to Jesus. (29) A great and powerful lord, over all nations and armies everywhere (*epidêmêsonta*)—that is what the prophets say. They did not announce this annoyance.

This argument does not assume any acceptance of the prophetic books; the argument is that the Christian scriptures themselves, the prophetic books of the Christian Old Testament, say nothing about anyone like

Jesus, but do say a lot about someone quite different. The same author draws arguments about the general nature of human thought from the myths and literature of paganism in 2:67, 2:34, and 2:55, while expressly saying in 2:67 that he does not believe the stories.

This is however, not the only solution. It is possible that the original reference was to prophecies, not prophets, and that the intention was to refer to the relevant passages in the Torah.¹⁰ It would be easy for a Jewish translator to turn prophecies into prophets. Also, **NBYH** *nibyā* “the Prophet” (singular) could have been read as **NBYH** (sic! with one yod) *nēbayyā* “the prophets” (plural) in both places, with the word “prophecies” having been read correctly. I prefer this second pair of explanations. The reference in 2:30 to “symbols and connotations” fits perfectly. Proofs from the books of the prophets, such as a reference to Isaiah 7:14, could be described as taken out of context and unnatural. However, it is the traditional proofs from the Torah, such as “a star will step forth out of Jacob” (Numbers 24:17) or “till Shiloh comes” (Genesis 49:10) that can be criticized as “symbols and connotations” or “symbols and conventional meanings” (*symbolai kai akousmata*).¹¹

V. THE JEWISH PREFACE

As the anonymous Samaritan composition stands, it is prefaced by a paragraph about Jesus’ birth and the start of his career (1:28,32,39). This preface is incompatible with what follows. It says that Jesus was born of adultery, a charge not made later even where it might have been relevant. It says that the mother gave birth in secret, whereas later on the story of the star is quoted (alluded to by Origen at 1:34 in anticipation of the quote at 1:58, but not quoted in full because Origen does not disagree); and the Magoi are mentioned at 1:58. Origen’s allusion in 1:34 is not taken from the preface, as can be seen if the passage is read carefully. Rather, it belongs with 1:58. The preface says that the mother fled to Egypt to escape her husband, whereas later on there is a clear mention of the flight from Herod (1:58). The preface also says that Jesus learnt magic in Egypt, a claim not appearing later on even where it might have been useful. All of these departures from the Gospels are incompatible with the justifiable assertion later on that all arguments used have been based on the Christian scriptures (2:13 and 2:74). There is also an explicit denial of the possibility or reasonableness of the conception of Jesus by divine power, a

¹⁰Genesis 49, Numbers 23-24, Deuteronomy 32, and most definitely Deuteronomy 33 as interpreted for the future, as well as single verses and short passages elsewhere, e.g. Deuteronomy 18:15-19. (On Deuteronomy 33, see the section, “Ancient Samaritan Eschatologies” [above, n. 8]).

¹¹Here the second term is a translation of a precise Aramaic and Hebrew term related to, or the same as, the Rabbinic technical term **ShMW**(II).

question not raised later on, even where it would have been relevant. Finally, the last sentence in the preface is "Thus there is nothing in all this about the Kingdom of God". There is no further reference to the Kingdom of God in the text. Also, the accusation that Jesus was the son of a soldier called Panthêra is specifically Jewish. The preface appears to reproduce known Jewish polemic going back to the late first century A.D. and first hinted at in Matthew 28:11-17. It is an addition to the anonymous treatise, taken from a readily available text, possibly added by the translator of the text that follows. Given the undoubted Jewishness of the preface, it is understandable that Kelsos thought the whole document to be Jewish in origin.

VI. THE DATE OF THE SAMARITAN TREATISE AND ITS PURPOSE

Clearly, the author is familiar with the Gospels of Matthew, Luke, and John, and perhaps all four. As we have seen, he knows of the star and the Magoi, from Matthew. In 2:18 there is an allusion to John 13:21-30 or Matthew 26:20-25. In 2:32 there is a reference to the genealogies of both Matthew 1 and Luke 3. In 2:44 there is a reference to John 12:33, and 18:32. In 2:76 there is an allusion to Matthew 11:20-24 or Luke 10:13-16. Other possible examples include an allusion to 1 Peter 3:18-20 and 4:6 at 2.43. The prominence of the argument against the quality of the evidence for Jesus' title of Son of God, and the insistence on the right of the inaugurator of the Day of Vengeance and Recompense to this title (see 1:41,49,50; the sentences are consecutive) reads like a refutation of Hebrews 3:1-6.

There are two further elements in the text which provide hints regarding the date. One is the question posed as to why the Christians want to be different to the disciples by their willingness to die (2:45). As there is no evidence of persecution of Christians by the Roman authorities in Palestine at this time, the explanation that fits best is that there was a policy of expelling Christians from a semi-independent or autonomous Samaria. The other is the term "fellow-citizens" by which the Christians are addressed in 2:1. While Samaritans could be found in large numbers outside Palestine, this form of address suggests a time when there was a definable Samaritan political and territorial entity in Samaria.¹²

¹²The reference to the mass conversion to Christianity in 2:4 as being only fairly recent is not as precise as it might seem. Literally, the words are "yesterday or the day before" (*khthes kai prôên*). This expression need only mean in historical time, as opposed to undateable antiquity. Note the use of this expression by Origen in 1.37. In the present context it probably means not so long ago as to be irreversible. In the section, "Ancient Samaritan Eschatologies" (above, n. 8), I have argued that the Samaritans must have been united when they successfully petitioned the Roman administration in AD 36-37 for the removal of Pontius Pi-

Obviously the Samaritan treatise had to be composed long enough before Kelsos wrote to be translated into Greek by Jews and for the Jewish preface to be added. This means the latest date for the treatise would be about AD 170. The likely earliest date is linked to events in Samaria. When the Samaritans consolidated and strengthened their place in Samaria after AD 135, they took over some areas that Jews had previously infiltrated. They also successfully invited Jews to renounce their heresy and identify with the Samaritan community.¹³ Such a setting explains the reference to the expulsion of Christians from Samaria, the use of ‘fellow-citizens’ and the apparent willingness of Christians to die. It also needs to be borne in mind that from the Samaritan viewpoint Christianity has a lot in common with Judaism. Although polemical, the treatise invites the readers to return from the error of their great-grandparents, and integrate with the society of their country. In short, a date from AD 135 (or even 133) right up till 170 are possible, with a date at the earlier end of the scale much more likely.

VII. THE PLACE OF THE ANONYMOUS SAMARITAN DOCUMENT IN THE HISTORY OF SAMARITAN THEOLOGY

As a postscript it is important to point out insights this treatise may provide into aspects of Samaritan theology. The polemical nature of the text

late, after he had massacred members of one faction. Presumably the murder of Libi and the separation of the various Dosithean groups from the rest and from each other in social and organisational matters occurred later. How much later is another question.

¹³On the invitation to the Jews, compare the Palestinian Talmud, Yevamot 8:3, 9d top; Kiddushin 4:1, 65c end. This passage is commonly misinterpreted to mean that thirteen Jewish towns were taken over by the Samaritans by straightforward expansion, but the two independent contexts and the precise technical terminology make it clear that the towns were *absorbed* (NSH^cTQ^cW) by intermarriage. This must have been accompanied by complete social absorption right from the start. Two towns are named, both to the north of Samaria, one of them being Marj^c Ayûn (on the correct readings see Jastrow under MWSh^cHN) The towns are termed ‘YRWT, not KPRYM, which means they must have been municipalities including some farmland. It says “in the time of the persecution” (ShMD) which would have been before and after AD 135. The Samaritan tradition asserts that the Samaritans had mixed fortunes under Hadrian but were much favoured by Antoninus Pius (Abu ‘I-Fateh. 115:14-118:7, in *Abulfathi Annales Samaritani*, ed. Eduardus Vilmar, Gotha 1865). There is an explicit statement of an expulsion of Jews from the centre of Samaria, apparently under Hadrian, but the arrangement of the text makes the exact dating uncertain. There is also a separate statement that Jews in Samaria were subject to Samaritan rule under licence from Rome, again apparently under Hadrian and his successor. This favourable situation ended with the policies of Commodus, which would have affected Palestine soon after AD 180. Note that Justin Martyr debated with the Jew, Trypho, outside Samaria. Note also that his knowledge of Jews came late, and from literary sources.

means it is selective in its choice of subjects. I hope to look at this question more fully at a later date.

For the moment, six observations warrant mention. One, the Day of Vengeance and Recompense is not necessarily eschatological. Two, the overall objection to Christianity is not its doctrine, but its failure to show that Jesus did what was necessary to embody that doctrine. The crucial sentences are as follows. "We do expect to be resurrected bodily and live forever, the one sent to us being the model and initiator, proving that it is not impossible for God to bodily resurrect someone. Where is he then, so that we can see and believe? (78) Did he only descend to make us not believe? (79) He was therefore only a man, as the truth makes clear and as reason shows" (2:77-79). Such a doctrine is in fact attested for some Dositheans. There are similar objections in 2:5, which says that there is nothing new in Christian eschatology in its concept of a universal resurrection and judgment. Three, there is no objection to the fact that Jesus was from the tribe of Judah rather than Levi. The Samaritan woman in John 4 saw no difficulty with such an identity. Four, there is no objection to the fact that Jesus was not Moses returned from an intermediate state of waiting.¹⁴ Five, there is no objection to the fact that the Mosaic Tabernacle and its vessels have not re-appeared. Not too much need be made of this omission, however, since the author might have wanted to avoid complicating the argument. Six, in 2:31, there is a rejection of the exposition of John 1. Unfortunately this is one of the few places where Origen uses indirect speech in part of his quotation, and abbreviates the argument slightly. "[He accuses the Christians of sophistry in saying that] the Son of God is himself the Logos". The sentence following, however, clarifies the accusation as being the double use of the term "Son of God" for both the "pure and holy Logos" and a mere human: in other words, it is the fallacy of letting a main term in a systematic exposition shift its meaning in the course of the exposition. If we accept the Epistle of the Apostles as a document of Samaritan Christianity, which seems reasonable in view of its insistent mention of Simon and Cerinthus, then it is certainly worth noting that this document deals implicitly but repeatedly and insistently with the solution to precisely this difficulty. The author of our anonymous document explicitly accepts the concept of the Logos in a way that the context indicates is significantly more than standard Neoplatonism.

¹⁴See the section, "Ancient Samaritan Eschatologies" (above, n. 8) on the pervasiveness of this concept in both Jewish and Samaritan sources.